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A Case Report On Unilateral Acute Proptosis Post Blunt Ocular Trauma

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ABSTRACT

In this article we present a case of Acute unilateral Proptosis with sudden, painful loss of vision following right eye trauma with tennis ball while playing cricket. The patient developed right eye retrobulbar haemorrhage along with subperiosteal hematoma but even after severe high intraocular pressure compressing the optic nerve had a complete visual recovery following orbital decompression surgery. We have tried to emphasis on the point of importance of surgical intervention in providing good visual recovery in severe tensed post-traumatic proptosis.

Keyword: Unilateral post-traumatic proptosis, retrobulbar haemorrhage, subperiosteal haemorrhage, orbital decompression, anterior orbitotomy, lateral canthotomy with cantholysis.

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INTRODUCTION

Retrobulbar haemorrhage is a complication from ocular trauma that may cause permanent vision loss. It can potentially lead to dangerous increase in intraocular pressure, a condition that is also described as orbital compartment syndrome¹. Vision loss from RBH results from bleeding into the orbit, which is a fixed retrobulbar (orbital) space closed posteriorly, superiorly and inferiorly by bone and limited anteriorly by the eyelids and canthal tendons. Due to retrobulbar space being surrounded by bone medially, laterally, and posteriorly, any increase in pressure in the space will result in a forward shift. Trauma or post-operative complications can lead to bleeding in the space, usually from the infraorbital artery or one of its branches.^{2,3} The eye can handle slight forward displacement, however any further proptosis can result in optic nerve defects, as the optic nerve reaches its stretch limitations. Essentially, retrobulbar hemorrhage results in a compartment syndrome which can lead to compression or ischemia of the optic nerve, blockage of the optic nerve venous drainage, or a central retinal arterial occlusion leading to vision loss.^{4,5} Surgery decompression of the orbit is recommended when visual deficit arises and when there is no response to pharmacologic therapy. Several techniques for orbital decompression have been proposed.⁶

CASE REPORT

A 13year old boy sustained Right eye blunt ocular trauma by tennis ball while playing cricket at his home. He presented in our OPD after 1week after trauma with complaints of

- Forward protrusion of Right eyeball since 1week
- Sudden, painful loss of vision since 1 week
- Watering since 1week
- Redness since 1week

History of presenting complaints:-

The prominence of right eye was acute in onset and progressive in nature. The proptosis was Ab-axial with eyeball pushed downward and outward. There was no history of fever, photophobia, tremors, palpitations, diplopia, postural variation, or increase in size with sneezing, coughing, and any history of seizure disorder. It was associated with sudden, progressive, painful loss of vision over time span of 4days.

Table 1: Ocular findings at time of presentation

Examination	Right eye	Left eye
Vision	HM+ PR accurate in all quadrant	6/6
External	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ab-axial proptosis around 30mm with downward displacement of 5mm, lateral displacement of 3mm • Lagophthalmos present 	Normal lid and cilia

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • complete ophthalmoplegia 	
Conjunctiva	Mixed circumcorneal + conjunctival congestion with severe chemosis grade 3	Clear
Cornea	Exposure keratitis involving inferior half with diffuse corneal edema	Bright
Anterior chamber Iris/ pupil	Depth normal, hypopyon around 1mm RAPD grade 1	Depth normal, content clear Iris pattern normal, pupil central, circular brisk reactive to light
Lens	Transparent	Transparent
Ocular motility	Restricted in all gazes	Ocular movement full and free in all gazes
Fundus	Disc hyperemic with blurred disc margin, blood vessels engorged in peripapillary area, cup disc ratio not appreciated.	Within normal limit

Figure 1: Showing Right eye ocular findings at the time of presentation; Ab-axial proptosis with severe chemosis and exposure keratopathy.

Investigations:

All the routine blood investigations were sent whose reports were within normal limit. NCCT (Head + Orbit) was done to find out the Etiology behind the presenting ocular signs.

Figure 2: Showing different sections of NCCT (Head + Orbit)

NCCT (HEAD+ORBIT) showed-

- No significant abnormalities in brain parenchyma.
- Fracture of roof of right orbit with subperiosteal hematoma.
- Retrobulbar hematoma in right orbit leading to compression and displacement of extra ocular muscle and eyeball with optic nerve compression.

Management:

Patient started on following medical treatment to reduce raised intraocular pressure and to prevent secondary infections.

Broad spectrum Antibiotics:-

- a) inj. Piperacillin+Tazobactam 2.5gm i.v twice a day
- b) inj. Metronidazole 300mg i.v thrice a day

Trypsin- Chymotrypsin to decrease swelling.

Tab. Acetazolamide 250mg BD to reduce raised intraocular pressure.

Topical medications (for exposure keratitis)-

- a) Fortified Vancomycin 5% 1hrly
- b) eyedrop Moxifloxacin 0.5% 1hrly
- c) Homatropine 2% TDS
- d) Topical beta blocker (Timolol 0.5%) BD
- e) Frequent instillation of topical lubricating drops.

All the topical medications were applied under protective eye patch to halt further exposure of cornea due to inadequate lid closure.

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT:-

Right eye orbital decompression was performed via Anterior orbitotomy approached through sub-brow incision for subperiosteal hematoma and lateral canthotomy along with lateral cantholysis for retrobulbar hematoma.

Figure 3: Showing surgical steps being performed during Orbital Decompression

Table 2: Ocular examination after surgical management:-

Examination	Right eye	Left eye
Vision	From 6/60 in POD 3 to 6/12 in POD-15	6/6
External	Resolved proptosis along with complete lid closure Sutured wound healthy	Normal lid and cilia
Conjunctiva	Clear	Clear
Cornea	Healed keratitis with leucomatous corneal opacity inferiorly sparing pupillary axis	Bright
Anterior chamber	Depth normal content clear	Depth normal content clear
Iris/pupil	Semi dilated under pharma	Central circular reactive to light
Lens	Transparent	Transparent
Ocular movement	Full and free all gazes	Full and free all gazes
Fundus	Resolved disc edema.	Within normal limit

Figure 4: Post operative improvement in Proptosis, Chemosis and Keratopathy in subsequent days

Patient visited in our OPD after 1 month of surgery with **complete resolution of Proptosis, Chemosis and Visual Acuity restoring to 6/6** which was a miraculous improvement after the sight threatening condition patient had at the time of admission.

Figure 5: Showing 1 month follow-up with complete resolution of Proptosis and a complete vision restoration to 6/6.

DISCUSSION

Orbital hematomas can be caused by trauma and can be classified as intraorbital or subperiosteal. Intraorbital hematomas show findings of subconjunctival hemorrhage, lid edema and bruising and diminished ocular movement. Subperiosteal hematomas, which occur secondary to rupture of subperiosteal blood vessels will present with proptosis, lid ecchymosis, and impairment of eye movement.⁷ Acute Proptosis following ocular trauma can also occur in orbital emphysema following orbital wall fracture.⁸

Hematoma are managed depending on the impairment of vision; without evidence of visual disturbance, the hemorrhage can be observed without specific treatment. When vision is affected, the hematoma should be drained.⁷ CT scan is the preferred imaging modality, to delineate the size and extent of these hematomas, and also to rule out associated orbital wall fractures.

In our case also our patient had Superior Subperiosteal Hemtoma and Retrobulbar Hemorrhage as delineated by CT scan been performed. Even after prolonged period of Optic Nerve Compression, after surgical Decompression, patient showed significant improvement in Proptosis as well as Visual Acuity.

In a case report published by Gupta et al in December 2022, they discussed about a similar case where A 13-year child presented with protrusion of the left eye (LE) with redness, pain, and diminution of vision following blunt head trauma. The best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) in the LE was hand movement. On examination, LE had abaxial proptosis with lagophthalmos and severe exposure keratopathy. They immediately drained the subperiosteal

fluid through USG guided aspiration by 18G needle.⁹ However due to exposure keratopathy followed by Leucomatous corneal opacity involving pupillary area there was no such significant visual recovery.

CONCLUSION

Retrobulbar Hemorrhage is a very serious complication in cases of Post-traumatic blunt ocular injury which can be sight threatening. However patient receiving proper and prompt treatment can have good visual recovery. Ideally after been diagnosed with vision affecting intraconal and subperiosteal hematoma, surgical intervention should be done within 2hours of presentation. But in our case, due to delayed presentation of the patient, even after so much of delay in the surgical intervention, our patient had a good visual recovery. Hence this is a Miraculous case of acute unilateral post traumatic proptosis.

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